

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LEATHER POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This work deals with the utilization of industrial leather wastes, such as Poly Vinyl Butyral (PVB) and post-consumer milk pouches, by preparing a composite material as a product that has commercial value and applications. Due to industrialization, there is an alarming rate of increase in solid wastes generated from the industrial operations day by day resulting in environmental pollution. This research describes utilization of industrial wastes such as buffing dust (leather industries), PVB (glass Industries) and Milk pouch a common household garbage and involves preparation and characterization of composites contents of various percentage. Post-consumer milk pouch film is a blend, consisting of LDPE/LLDPE (50:50). Laminated glass is a sandwich made of one sheet of plastic Poly Vinyl Butyral between two or more glasses. The PVB sticks to the glass by forming chemical as well as mechanical bonds. When laminated with annealed glass, the layer maintains the geometric integrity of the pane in case of breakage. Buffing dust and Post-consumer milk pouch are compounded using two roll mill at a temperature of 403 K. At this temperature both wastes are mixed and stacked together. After milling, the composite sheets were compression molded at a temperature of 368 K and about 20 ton of pressure to form sheets. Also similar process is done with PVB. Samples of 3 mm thickness were for conducting mechanical tests. To find out the properties of composites sheets, the sheets were punched out as per ASTM standard for testing the tensile properties, hardness, abrasion resistance and tear strength. The properties are compared with PVB and LDPE/LLDPE composites. Thus waste materials have been successfully utilized as filler in polymer composites to produce useful materials suitable for industrial applications. This not only reduces the production cost and material cost, but also offers an opportunity for utilization of waste materials and thereby reducing environmental pollution.

1 INTRODUCTION

Generation of solid and liquid wastes during manufacturing processes is unavoidable in major industries. India alone produces; more than 960MT of solid waste from various industrial and domestic operations. Dumping of these wastes in wastelands pose severe environmental threat. Proper recycling of the wastes would certainly save the energy and conserve the resources. Residue

management has become a major problem in modern society, especially solid residue that poses potential toxic effects [1]. The search for innovative solutions for the reuse of solid residue increased in the late 20th century and has intensified with growing urgency for environmental preservation [2-4]. Many residue management solutions aim to add value to residue through the development of new materials and processes. [5-7] Leather deposition is a serious matter because, under certain pH and temperature conditions, the chromium used during the tanning process can undergo valence change, going from trivalent chromium (Cr+3) to hexavalent chromium (Cr+6), a highly toxic and carcinogenic metal [2]. Thus, if leather waste is disposed in nature, it can contaminate rivers, lakes and underground water consequently, and can affect animals and plants. A huge quantity of polyethylene, specially Low density polyethylene (LDPE) and Linear Low Density Polyethylene (LLDPE), is consumed for flexible packaging of liquid in India. It has been reported that the consumption of packaging liquid milk is increasing day by day. In practice, such a packaging trend results in accumulation of huge volume of polyethylene packaging wastes after a short service life causing serious environmental threat to the society. Poly vinyl butyral is a vinyl butyral and vinyl alcohol amorphous random copolymer produced by the condensation of polyvinyl alcohol with butyraldehyde in the presence of an acidic catalyst. Its elastic properties, toughness and greater adhesion to inorganic materials such as glass can be determined according to the percentage of each monomer in the chain. The main application of PVB is in laminated safety glass manufacturing especially in automotive, aerospace and architectural glass sectors. The recycling of plastic packaging materials is increasing rapidly to develop new value added plastic products. The present study, deals with development of composites using leather wastes viz., buffing dust with Poly Vinyl Butyral (PVB) and Post-consumer Milk pouches with 50% composition and evaluating its properties. Further, the mechanical properties of leather polymer composites was studied by analyzing their tensile strength, abrasive resistance, elongation at break, shore hardness, tear strength and scanning electron micrograph analysis.

2 MATERIALS

2.1 Buffing Dust (BD)

Considerable amount of leather wastes are produced during every operation of transforming raw skin to leather as a final product. Each operation leads to the generation of different kinds of wastes. During each stage of processing, tannery generates huge amount of solid wastes. For this study, we have considered only buffing dust (Fig.1(a)). Buffing dust from chrome tanned leather which is portentous, impregnated with chromium, synthetic fat, oil, tanning agents and dye chemicals is one of the difficult tannery wastes to manage. Leather wastes and buffing dusts were collected from leather industry, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India.

2.2 Poly Vinyl Butyral (PVB)

Laminated glass is a sandwich made of one piece of plastic Poly Vinyl Butyral (Fig.1(b)) between two or more glasses. Car windshields and laminated safety glass consists of a sandwich of a PVB film between two glass sliders. These products generate a large volume of PVB that has not yet been widely destined for recycling. Because of molecular structure and the presence of plasticizers, the PVB used in automotive glass has properties similar to elastomer. The PVB sticks with the glass, forms chemical as well as mechanical bonds. When laminated with annealed glass, the layer maintains the geometric integrity of the pane in case of breakage. Also it gives acoustic insulation as well as gives protection against damage caused due to UV radiation as it cuts almost 99% of UV radiation present in the sunlight. [2]

2.3 Post Consumer Milk Pouch

Post-Consumer milk pouches are (fig.1(c)), composed of low density polyethylene (LDPE) and Linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE) with 50:50 (w/w)[8-10]. These Milk pouches were collected from the municipal dustbin, India. The collected waste films were contaminated with small amounts of possible pigment, stabilizer, slip agent and labelling dye etc.

Figure 1: Materials (a) Buffing Dust (b) Poly Vinyl Butyral (c) Post-consumer milk pouch

3 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

3.1 PREPARATION OF BUFFING DUST

In the present study, leather wastes called buffing dust was collected from tannery. The buffing dust may contain foreign particles. These particles were removed by sieving process using suitable mesh size. And then buffing dust were dried under direct sunlight to remove moisture present in it. It was found that the initial weight was reduced by 10% in buffing dust. Also the average particle size of leather buffing dust was found to be 500nm using particle size analyzer using propanol as a dispersant.

3.2 PREPARATION OF MILK POUCHES

The milk pouches are manufactured using LDPE and LLDPE blend. The sequence of post-consumer milk pouches are shown in fig.2. The milk pouches were taken from municipal garbage. The collected milk pouches were washed with a hot aqueous solution at 60deg, with detergent followed by repeated washing with cold water. At this stage the labeling dyes are removed. The cleaned milk pouches were dried under direct sunlight.

Figure 2: Pre Treatment of milk pouches

4. PREPARATION OF COMPOSITES

Formulations of leather polymer composites with Poly vinyl Butyral and post-consumer milk pouch are taken as 50:50(wt%). Laboratory scale two roll rubber mixing mill with roll dimension D=220 mm and

L=450mm was used for the preparation of leather polymer composites. For preparing the composites, two roll mill which is generally used for rubber compounding was used for mixing the components. The two rolls were turned towards each other with preset, adjustable nip or gap to allow the material to pass through to achieve high- shear mixing at 95°C. The material is fed from the top of the roll mill. The gap between the rollers was maintained at 1mm. The back roll usually turns at a faster surface speed than the front mill. Back roll was rotated at 15rpm and front roll at 10 rpm. After the compounding materials were placed on the lower die, The dies were heated up to 95°C. Then the upper die is compressed against lower die at 20KN pressure. Then it was allowed to cool in the die itself for half an hour. The compounded material was taken out of the die with the aid of the ejector pin.

5. CHARECTERIZATION OF PREPARED COMPOSITES

5.1 Tensile Test

Dumbbell specimens for tensile test were prepared as per ASTM D638. The tensile properties of both the composites manufactured were conducted on the universal testing machine, using a cross head speed of 50mm/min. Three test specimens of each composition were tested.

5.2 Hardness

The hardness was measured according to ASTM D2240 standard method at room temperature and expressed in shore D hardness scale.

5.3 Morphology (SEM)

To study the morphological features of fiber-matrix interfaces in the composite samples, the tensile test samples were fractured and mounted on Aluminium stubs, which were coated with gold using sputter coater. The gold coated samples were analyzed by a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The micrographs of the surface and cross section were obtained by operating SEM at an accelerating voltage of 12kV and at different magnifications.

5.4 Abrasion Resistance

Abrasion resistance of the samples was determined by means of DuPont abrader machine. Composite samples of the required size were held against the abrasive wheel (CS-10) at 30 rpm speed. Tests were conducted for 1000 cycles. Weight loss in the samples before and after the abrasion provides abrasion resistance.

5.5 Tear Resistance

Tear test specimens were prepared as per ASTM D1004. Tear resistance result shows the ability of resistance towards tear load of prepared leather polymer composites. Test were conducted at a speed of 50mm/min. Three test specimens of each compositions were tested.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The present study summarizes the development and characterization of polymer composites using leather wastes, viz., buffing dust as fillers with different polymer materials.

Table 1: Property comparisons between two different composites

Property	Unit	PVB: BD (50:50)	MP:BD (50:50)
Tensile Strength	Mpa	8	10
Abrasion Resistance	Mg	172	8
Tear resistance	N	84	225
Hardness	Shore D	39	57

Leather fibers are mainly composed of collagen, which consists of long amino acid chains, chromium

FIGURE 3: Micrographs of prepared composites a) PVB: BD (50:50) b) MP: BD (50:50)

Figure 3(a) presents micrograph of fractured surface of the PVB/ leather samples and figure 3(b) shows the micrograph of the Milk Pouch/ Leather composites samples where leather fibers appear to be well distributed in the PVB and Milk pouch samples. A good interfacial bonding was observed by the continuity of the leather fiber agglomerates with the PVB and Milk pouch Matrices. It is usually difficult to achieve good adhesion between a thermoplastic matrix and natural fiber due to different chemical and physical properties of hydrophilic fibers which is composed of collagen macromolecules and hydrophobic thermoplastic matrices. One way to improve the interfacial adhesion and obtain continuous surfaces in thermoplastic composites with natural fibers is to use coupling agents or compatibilizers. Good adhesion resulting at the interface of the leather composites without addition of coupling agents or compatibilizers may be due to good interaction between the PVB matrix and the leather fiber agglomerates. The tensile strength tends to increase slightly in the Milk pouch leather composites. The mechanical properties of fiber reinforced composites depend not only on the characteristics of polymer matrices and the reinforcement fibers but also on the interface between the matrix and the fiber, which is important for the transfer of interfacial stress. The abrasion resistance of the composites mainly depends on the matrix phase. The Milk pouch/ Leather polymer composites has superior abrasion resistance compared to PVB/Leather polymer composites. The tear strength of the Leather composites indicates the dependence on the matrix phase. Milk pouch /leather composites shows the superior tear strength over the PVB/leather composites. The Hardness of PVB/leather composites shows that the proposed composites are flexible and soft material because of

the PVB which is a very flexible and one kind of elastomer. The hardness of the milk pouch leather composite is a kind of hard plastic. The mechanical properties of the leather composites are strongly influenced by the matrix phase. The properties of hardness, wear resistance and tear resistance of the leather polymer composites were considered satisfactory and showed behaviors expected for this type of composites.

7. CONCLUSION

A comparative study on mechanical properties of PVB and milk pouch based leather composites were carried out in the present study. Based on this study, it can be concluded that the post-consumer milk pouch and PVB could find suitable applications as polymer matrix. Also this provides the possible solution for the solid management of solid wastes generated by the leather industry and house hold wastes. This leather polymer composites provides good mechanical properties for this particular combination. The properties of hardness, abrasion resistance, tear resistance, tensile strength of the prepared leather polymer composites were considered satisfactory and showed behaviors expected for this type of composites. The leather polymer composite sheets thus produced can find numerous applications in a variety of industries.

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